

IMPLEMENTATION STUDY APPROACH TOWARDS IMPROVING BIOSAFETY INITIATIVES AT KAKAMEGA MUNICIPALITY IN KAKAMEGA COUNTY, KENYA

Date

01/03/2024

yyyy-mm-dd

hh:mm

Age (in years)

E.g, 17

Sex

- Male
- Female

Level of education

- Never went to school
- Some primary
- Some secondary
- Some post secondary

Location

- Municipal market
- Open air market
- Learning institution
- Shop
- Hotel
- Health facility
- Residential area

How long have you worked in this area?

- <6 months
- 1 year
- > 1 year
- >3 years
- >5 years
- >7 years
- >9 years
- >10 years

Type of business

- Boutique
- Second hand clothes
- Butchery
- General grocery
- Vegetable grocery
- Shop/supermarket
- Milk
- Electronics/phones
- Spare parts
- Cereals
- Hotel/eatery
- Healthcare
- Education
- Not applicable

What kind of health facility?

- County referral hospital
- Private hospital
- Dispensary
- Health centre

What type of learning institution?

- University (MMUST)
- University (other)
- College
- Secondary GoK
- Secondary private
- Primary GoK
- Primary private
- Kindegarten

Does your business activity generate waste?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what type of waste?

- Non infectious
- Solid
- Liquid
- Infectious
- Highly infectious
- E-waste
- Sharps
- Radiological

Do you know how properly waste management should be done?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what are the considerations in managing waste?

- Waste Collection
- Waste Storage
- Waste Sorting
- Waste Recording
- Waste Transportation
- Waste Disinfection
- Waste Disposal
- Waste Re-use
- Waste Recycling

Do you understand the effects of poor waste management?

- Yes
- No

If yes, name some of the effects of poor waste management

- Disease outbreak
- Accidents (pricks,cuts,etc)
- Air pollution
- Water contamination
- Soil contamination
- Dirty working environment
- Climate change

Have you ever attended any training/mentorship/sensitization meeting on waste management?

- Yes
- No

If yes, how long ago was the training/mentorship/sensitization meeting you attended?

- 1-3 months ago
- 4-6 months ago
- 7-9 months ago
- 10-12 months ago
- More than 12 months ago

Do you know of any county government initiative towards waste management?

- Yes
- No

If yes, which are some of the county government initiatives to waste management?

- Waste collectors
- Waste bins in the market
- Three waste bins in strategic places
- Waste pit
- Waste transporters

Have you at any time utilized the county waste management initiatives described above?

- Yes
- No

If yes, which county government initiatives listed have you used

- Waste collectors
- Waste bins in the market
- Three waste bins in strategic places
- Waste pit
- Waste transporters

If you have never used the county government waste management initiatives, what is your reason for not using them?

- They are not accessible
- They are paid for
- I don't know how to use them
- I burn my own wastes

Have you ever spent on waste management?

- Yes
- No

If yes, how much on average do you spend on waste per week?

- 10-30 shillings
- 40-60 shillings
- 70-90 shillings
- 100-120 shillings
- 130-150 shillings
- More than 150 shillings

What is your average profit from your business per week?

- Less than 100 shillings
- 100-200 shillings
- 200-300 shillings
- 300-400 shillings
- 400-500 shillings
- >500 shillings
- Not willing to disclose
- Not for profit

How much are you willing to spend on waste if one has to spend on it?

- <50 shillings
- 50-70 shillings
- 70-90 shillings
- 90-110 shillings
- 110-130 shillings
- 130-150 shillings
- >150 shillings
- Not willing to spend

Any comment you would want to be considered?

Submitted by

- Boaz
- Sibitare
- Brian
- Leonard
- Muriuki
- Hanson
- Faith
- Vallary
- Ephantus
- Aggrey
- Levis
- Eliphalet
- Carolyne
- Sakwa
- Emmaculate